

The Impact of Price, Facilities and Experience in Maintaining the Sustainable Loyalty of Air Asia Passengers Using Satisfaction as a Mediating Variable

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Abstract:- This study aims to analyze the influence of price, facilities, and experience on the sustainable loyalty of AirAsia airline passengers, with satisfaction as the mediating variable. Airlines, especially low-cost ones, play an important role in the air transportation industry in Indonesia, which has a vast archipelago and high mobility needs. The research method used is quantitative using Jamovi software. The sample used was 106 respondents, collected through an online questionnaire in December 2024. The results of this study show that passenger satisfaction functions as a significant mediator in the relationship between price, facilities, and experience to passenger loyalty. These findings emphasize the importance of creating a positive experience for passengers to increase their satisfaction and loyalty to the airline.

Keywords:- Price, Facilities, Experience, Satisfaction, Loyalty, Mediation Variables.

I. INTRODUCTION

Airlines are one of the modes of air transportation with more diverse options because airlines offer a wide range of speed and coverage. For Indonesia, which is an archipelagic country, the role of airline companies is one of the most important air transportation options, because it is able to reach almost all areas of the country [1]

Low Cost Carrier (LCC) is an aviation industry concept that offers low ticket costs and basic flight facilities, low-cost airlines are very popular in Indonesia. Low-cost airlines are competing to get the affection of passengers. In essence, the items provided are always based on the principle of low cost, which emphasizes and lowers operating costs to reach a wider lower market segment, the presence of low-cost airlines is very beneficial to the lower middle class economy, which starts from reasonable fares, modern fleets, and good service [2]. The LCC business concept in the aviation world is intended to expand market share and in order to maintain customer loyalty so that it becomes a loyal customer in a sustainable manner.

Passenger satisfaction plays a very important role in maintaining the company's business continuity. By creating a good relationship between the company and passengers, it will encourage sustainable passenger loyalty. Loyalty that continues to be maintained also affects the image of service providers [3]

Every industry certainly has its views and goals to realize the set goals, and the most important thing is to maximize sales and accessibility of the ease of obtaining products so that it can provide satisfaction and loyalty for passengers. Over the past fifteen years, Air Asia has managed to survive as the cheapest airline in the world (AirAsia, 2024). With more than twenty-three years of experience, and with eight innovative operational hubs in Asia, Air Asia continues to improve the passenger experience supported by world-class safety standards.

This study aims to analyze the influence of price, facilities, and experience on the sustainable loyalty of Air Asia airline passengers, by looking at the mediating role of passenger satisfaction in influencing passenger loyalty.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Fundamental Theory

This research uses a fundamental theory called the Theory of Reasoned Action developed by Vallerand. This theory explains that subjective attitudes and norms affect a person's intentions, which in turn will influence their behavior. In this case, factors such as price, amenities, and experience will shape passengers' attitudes towards their satisfaction. When passengers feel satisfied, that satisfaction will affect their intention to continue using the product or service, which will eventually be reflected in real behavior, such as the decision to repurchase or recommend the product/service. Satisfaction serves as a mediating variable that links the influence of price, amenities, and experience on passenger behavior through the feelings of satisfaction they experience. [5]

B. Price

Prices have many forms and various functions, such as rental costs, wages/fees, employee salaries, fuel purchases and others. All of these are forms of expenditure needed to obtain goods or services [6].

According to Kotler & Armstrong [7] price is the amount of money spent to obtain a product or service, or the value that consumers provide in order to enjoy the benefits, ownership, and use of the product or service.

Based on the opinion of Mursid [8] there are three dimensions and price indicators that can be described, namely, cost-oriented pricing, demand-oriented pricing, and competition-oriented pricing.

C. Facilities

Lupioadi [9] argues that facilities can be defined as a representation of the appearance, function, and condition of infrastructure facilities and the surrounding environment in an effort to show their existence to external parties. These facilities include physical elements such as buildings, equipment, and supporting equipment.

Facilities are a very crucial element in the service industry, especially in the airport sector. Therefore, the printing is to consider the condition of the facilities, both in terms of interior and exterior design, as well as cleanliness in order to meet the main needs of consumers properly [10].

Facilities are one of the main factors that affect passengers' decisions in choosing transportation services. The more complete the facilities provided, the more comfortable passengers will be in enjoying services during the trip [11].

According to Tjiptono [12] there are four indicators of facilities, namely: a). Special considerations or planning. Various aspects such as promotion, texture, color, and other elements, are considered, combined, and developed to elicit an intellectual and emotional response from the user or the person observing it; b). Spatial planning. These elements include interior and architectural arrangements, including the placement of pre-construction and fixtures in the space; c) Equipment and furniture. Equipment and furnishings serve as a means to provide comfort, act as decorative elements, or become supporting infrastructure for users and passengers; and d) Lighting and prabatan. Lighting includes setting the type of color, space color, and lighting that is adjusted to the activities being carried out and the desired layout.

D. Experience

According to Shaw and Ivens, experience is an internal and subjective response from passengers that arises as a result of interaction, either directly or indirectly, with various changes that exist in the environment [13]. Passenger experience when using airline services is one of the important factors for consumers today. Maintaining passenger loyalty requires a strategy that not only focuses on quality, but also on the overall passenger experience in order to increase passenger satisfaction [14]. Research by Kuniawan and Budiarti shows that there are three indicators of experience, namely, the taste and quality of the product, the quality of service and the interaction of the level of comfort felt.[15].

E. Passenger Satisfaction

According to Tjiptono & Chandra, increased passenger satisfaction can drive sales growth in both the long and short term, as well as expand market share through repurchases. On the other hand, passenger dissatisfaction actually provides an opportunity for companies to identify weaknesses in products or services that do not meet consumer expectations or set standards. [6].

According to Kotler, satisfaction is defined as a person's emotional state that can be in the form of satisfaction or disappointment, which arises as a result of a comparison between the performance of a product or service compared to the real experience received [16]. Passengers' expectations are formed through previous experiences, testimonials from others, and promotional activities. If passengers' expectations are not met by the performance of the product or service, then passengers tend to feel disappointed. On the other hand, if the performance meets or exceeds expectations, passengers will feel satisfied. This satisfaction creates a positive emotional bond between passengers and the Company, which can ultimately increase passenger loyalty.

Based on Lupiyoadi's view, passenger satisfaction indicators include several important aspects, namely, the suitability of expectations, the desire to make additional transactions, and the willingness to advise [17].

F. Passenger Loyalty

According to Kotler and Keller, passenger loyalty is the consumer's effort to maintain their loyalty, driven by a deep awareness of quality, satisfaction, and happiness in a product, which then encourages them to make a repeat purchase, while according to Cristopher and Luuren, loyalty is the passenger's desire to continue to have a long- term relationship with the company, through the purchase and repeated use of products and services. and voluntarily recommend the company's products or services to others [18]

According to Griffin, there are four indicators of passenger loyalty, namely a). consistently making repeat purchases, i.e. certain products continue to be purchased by passengers; b). acquisition of various categories of products and services, i.e. passengers buying product and service lines from the same company in addition to the main goods and services; and d). providing product recommendations, i.e. passengers discussing goods through word-of-mouth promotion; this indicates overall immunity to competition or passengers will not use other goods or services from competing companies [17] With motivation like this, it will make customers loyal on a sustainable basis

G. Relationship Between Variables and Research Framework

➤ *The Relationship Between Price and Loyalty*

Price is a variable that can be adjusted and is a determining factor in whether or not a product is accepted by consumers. As one of the main attributes that consumers consider, it is important to monitor the prices set by competitors. This is so that the company does not set prices that are too high or too low. Thus, the price offered can encourage consumers to remain loyal to the product or service. However, passenger loyalty may change if the Company implements a pricing policy that passengers deem unreasonable. Passengers who are aware of the price of the service will know the quality of the service they receive according to the amount of money they spend [19].

- **H1:** Price has a significant effect on loyalty.

➤ *The Relationship Between Facilities and Loyalty.*

The facilities provided by airlines have a significant role in shaping passenger loyalty. Adequate facilities, such as comfort, cleanliness, and good service, can increase passenger satisfaction. Research shows that good amenities have a positive effect on passenger satisfaction, which in turn can increase their loyalty to the airline [20].

- **H2:** Facilities have a significant effect on loyalty.

➤ *The relationship between experience and loyalty*

Passenger experience and loyalty have a very important relationship in a company, passenger experience includes all interactions that passengers experience with something, product, or service, which can create a certain impression and perception. According to Miharha [21] positive experiences have a significant effect on passenger loyalty. Passengers who have good experiences tend to be more loyal and often use the same service. This experience is not only limited to the quality of service, but also includes comfort, attention to passenger needs, and pleasant interaction during the service.

- **H3:** Experience has a significant effect on loyalty .

➤ *The Relationship between Price and Satisfaction*

There is a strong correlation between satisfaction and the price set for passengers. When prices go up, people demand better service, which in turn increases passenger satisfaction. In addition, the price that passengers pay is determined by the benefits they receive, and the price that influences their expectations can result in satisfied passengers [22] Price has a positive and significant relationship with passenger satisfaction. This is because cheap and affordable tickets can increase their satisfaction [23].

- **H4:** Price has a significant effect on satisfaction.

➤ *The Relationship between Amenities and Satisfaction*

A study based on [9] have a positive and significant influence on consumer satisfaction. This means that small changes to facilities can lead to larger changes to consumer satisfaction.

- **H5:** Facilities have a significant effect on satisfaction.

➤ *The Relationship between Experience and Satisfaction.*

Satisfaction is positively influenced by experience. This shows that experience is a strategic process in managing or implementing experience after purchasing a product. Therefore, business people must pay attention to passenger satisfaction so that companies can consider their passengers and encourage them to return. Passengers will feel satisfied, motivated to use the product or service again, and recommend it to others [24].

- **H6:** experiences have a significant effect on satisfaction.

➤ *The Relationship between Satisfaction and Loyalty.*

Increased passenger satisfaction has the potential to drive sales growth in both the long and short term, as well as increase market share through the repurchase of Tjiptono & Chandra [6] High satisfaction can strengthen passenger loyalty, reduce passenger turnover rate, and reduce price sensitivity [25]

- **H7:** Satisfaction has a significant effect on loyalty.

➤ *The Relationship Between Price and Loyalty Mediated by Satisfaction.*

Dimiyati and Subagio explained that price has a positive and significant influence on airline passenger loyalty. [6] This means that if the price offered by the airline is considered good by passengers, then their loyalty will increase. Thus, unreasonable prices only have a significant impact on passenger satisfaction but also directly affect loyalty, so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between price and loyalty that can occur directly or indirectly through satisfaction.

- **H8:** Passenger satisfaction significantly mediates the effect of price on loyalty.

➤ *The Relationship of Facilities to Satisfaction Mediated Loyalty.*

Loyalty and satisfaction are inseparable. Although there is still debate, both practitioners and academics generally agree that satisfaction and loyalty are inextricably linked. The relationship between the two is asymmetrical, as most loyal passengers are satisfied passengers, but not all forms of satisfaction can result in Oliver loyalty [13] This is in line with what Audistiana said that facilities and satisfaction have an effect on loyalty.[26]

- **H9:** Passenger satisfaction significantly mediates the effect of amenities on loyalty.

➤ *The Relationship of Experience to Loyalty Mediated by Satisfaction.*

Passenger satisfaction has a significant role as a mediator in the relationship between experience and loyalty. The main factor that affects loyalty is satisfaction itself. Passenger satisfaction is formed through the learning process that occurs in consumers. As individuals who have the ability to learn, consumers will pay attention and learn from previous experiences to determine the actions to be taken in the future. So, if consumers are satisfied with the product or service provided, they are more likely to make a repeat purchase. Positive experiences obtained, such as friendly and courteous attitudes from employees and service quality that meets passenger expectations, can increase their satisfaction and loyalty [27].

- **H10:** Passenger satisfaction significantly mediates the influence of experience on passenger loyalty.

H. Conceptual Framework of the Research

Based on the previous assessment, the framework of the research concept can be described as follows:

Fig 1: Cons Subjective Framework of the Research

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Population and Sample

This study uses a quantitative approach, with the population of all Air Asia passengers in Indonesia. A sample of 106 respondents was randomly selected using a google form. The number of samples was determined by the Roscoe method. The data was collected in December 2024, using a questionnaire distributed online to respondents who had used Air Asia. The questionnaire is designed to collect information about the various variables studied.

B. Research Variables

This study uses four variables, namely: Price (X1), Facility (X2), Experience (X3), Satisfaction (S), and Loyalty (L).

C. Measurement Scale

Each respondent was asked to provide an assessment response to various statements that had been prepared based on the research variables, using a rating scale scale of 1 – 10. Scale 1 shows the condition of the assessment level of Very Agree, while scale 10 shows the condition of the assessment level of Very Disagree. With this longer interval scale, it is hoped that respondents can express their opinions in more detail. The selection of the scale aims to increase the sensitivity of the data, a wide scale, and the variety of data describes the perception of the respondents more accurately.

IV. ANALYSIS METHODS

➤ *To Prove the Hypothesis, a Mediation Test with JAMOWI Software was used, with the Following Steps:*

- Data description, with the aim of obtaining an overview of the distribution of respondent data
- Validity and reliability tests, The validity test was used to determine the quality of the respondents' data using a loading factor with a minimum value of 0.6 and a probvalue of <0.05, while the reliability test was used to determine the consistency of respondents' answers, using Cronbach's criteria α a minimum of 0.7.
- Mediation test, In regression analysis, an indirect relationship between two variables is sometimes found through regression analysis. Both are mediated by a single variable. We call this intermediate variable an intervening variable or mediator. A variable is considered a mediator if it affects the relationship between the predictor (independent) and criterion (dependent) variables. Mediation tests were conducted to understand whether the influence of independent variables on dependent variables occurred directly or through variable mediators. They propose three basic steps in the mediation test [28]
 - ✓ Variable independent must significantly affect dependent variables.
 - ✓ The mediator variable must significantly affect the dependent variable.
 - ✓ The influence of independent variables on dependent variables should be reduced or become insignificant when mediators are incorporated into the model.

Fig 2: Relationship between Variable in Mediation Test.

Figure 2 shows the relationship between variables in the mediation test:

- The independent variable (X) affects the dependent variable (Y) directly with the path c.
- The independent variable (X) also affects the dependent (Y) indirectly through the mediator variable (M) with paths a and b.

Zhao developed the type of mediation from Baron and Kenny by identifying three consistent mediation patterns and two consistent patterns without mediation [29] as follows:

- Complementary mediation, if the direct effect (c) and the mediated effect (axb) are both significant in the same direction.
- Competitive mediation, if both the direct effect (c) and the mediated effect (axb) are significant and show opposite directions.
- Indirect-only mediator, i.e. if there is no direct effect (c is not significant), but there is a significant mediated effect (axb).
- Direct-only non mediation, i.e. if there is no indirect effect (axb is not significant), but there is a direct effect (c significant)).
- No-effect non-mediation, i.e. if there is no direct or indirect effect (axb and c are not significant).

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

A. Data Description

Table 1: Respondent Data is based on Gender, Age, Education, and Occupation

Reserch Description		Tot	Percent	All Respondent
Gender	Male	39	36,79%	106
	Famele	67	63,21%	
Age	<20	19	17,92%	
	21-30	50	47,17%	
	31-40	19	17,92%	
	>40	18	16,98%	
Last Education	Senior Hight School	61	57,55%	
	Diploma III	3	2,83%	
	Bachelor	31	29,25%	
	Master degree	9	8,49%	
	Other	2	1,89%	
Work	Student	52	49,05%	
	Private Sector Employee	14	13,21%	
	Employee	14	13,21%	
	Self-Employed	17	16,98%	
	Outher	9	8,49%	

Source: Data Processing

A total of 106 respondents, consisting of a total of 39 male respondents (36.79%), and 67 female respondents (63.21%). Based on age, 19 respondents (17.2%) were <20 years old, 50 respondents (47.27%) were 21-30 years old, 19 respondents (17.92%) were 31-40 years old, and 18 respondents (16.98) were over 40 years old. Based on the level of education with the last education in senior high school as many as 61 respondents (57.55%), diploma III as many as 3 respondents (2.83%),

bachelor as many as 31 respondents (29.25%), master degree as many as 9 respondents (8.49%), and others as many as 2 respondents (1.89%). When viewed from jobs with student occupations, there were 52 respondents (49.05%), private sector employees as many as 14 respondents (13.21%), employees as many as 14 respondents (13.21%), self-employed as many as 17 respondents (16.98%), and outers as many as 9 respondents (8.49%).

B. Validity Test

Table 2: Factor Loadings

Factor	Indicator	Estimate	SE	Z	p
Price	p1	1.018	0.1373	7.42	<.001
	p2	1.338	0.1564	8.56	<.001
	p3	1.004	0.1274	7.88	<.001
	p4	1.219	0.1339	9.10	<.001
	p5	0.935	0.1425	6.56	<.001
	p6	1.419	0.1300	10.92	<.001
Facility	f1	1.259	0.1136	11.08	<.001
	f2	1.460	0.1555	9.39	<.001
	f3	1.207	0.1274	9.47	<.001
	f4	1.328	0.1293	10.27	<.001
	f5	1.165	0.1199	9.72	<.001
	f6	1.188	0.1118	10.62	<.001
Experince	e1	1.247	0.1090	11.44	<.001
	e2	1.173	0.1161	10.10	<.001
	e3	1.186	0.1194	9.93	<.001
	e4	1.319	0.1297	10.16	<.001
	e5	1.246	0.1170	10.65	<.001
	e6	1.130	0.1306	8.65	<.001
Satisfaction	s1	1.393	0.1269	10.98	<.001
	s2	1.229	0.1024	12.00	<.001
	s3	1.302	0.1163	11.19	<.001
	s4	1.143	0.1034	11.05	<.001
	s5	1.172	0.1070	10.94	<.001
	s6	1.067	0.0984	10.84	<.001
Loyalty	l1	1.203	0.1197	10.05	<.001
	l2	1.185	0.1155	10.26	<.001
	l3	1.250	0.1535	8.14	<.001
	l4	1.348	0.1466	9.20	<.001
	l5	1.199	0.1181	10.16	<.001
	l6	1.376	0.1252	11.00	<.001

Source: Data Processing

The validity test can be carried out by correlation of Pearson's product moment with a limit value of 0.6 or it can also use facor loading with a $p < 0.05$ value criterion. Table 2 shows that the factor loading of all indicators in each variable has a p value (probvalue) < 0.05 . This shows that all indicators for each variable are valid, as a measure of the related variables used in the study. The implication is that all indicators and variables can be used for its advanced analysis.

C. Reliability Test

Table 3: Reliability Test

Scale Reliability Statistics	
	Cronbach's α
scale	0.978

Table 4: Reliability Test

Item Reliability Statistics	
	If item dropped
	Cronbach's α
p1	0.978
p2	0.978

p3	0.978
p4	0.977
p5	0.978
p6	0.977
f1	0.977
f2	0.977
f3	0.977
f4	0.977
f5	0.977
f6	0.977
e1	0.977
e2	0.977
e3	0.977
e4	0.977
e5	0.977
e6	0.977
s1	0.977
s2	0.977
s3	0.977
s4	0.977
s5	0.977
s6	0.977

11	0.977
12	0.977
13	0.977
14	0.977
15	0.977
16	0.977

The reliability test was used to test the consistency of respondents' answers. One of the uses is using Cronbach's α , with a minimum limit of 0.7. If Cronbach's score is $\alpha > 0.7$, it means that the respondent's answer is consistent, and if Cronbach's $\alpha < 0.7$, it means that the respondent's answer is not reliable. From tables 3 and 4, it is known that Cronbach's α values are all greater than 0.7 (range 0.977-0.978). This figure shows that all indicators and variables are highly reliable. Each item makes a good contribution, and identifies that this scale is very consistent and reliable for stable data results.

D. Mediation Test

Table 5: GLM Mediation Model

Mediators Models	m1	Satisfaction ~ Price + Facility + Experience
Full Models	m2	Loyalty ~ Satisfaction + Price + Facility + Experience
Indirect Effect (IE)	IE 1	Price=> Satisfaction => Loyalty
	IE 2	Facility=> Satisfaction=> Loyalty
	IE 3	Experience=>Satisfaction=> Loyalty
Sample size	N	106

The results of this GLM Mediation Model show the relationship between several variables that affect loyalty through passenger satisfaction as a mediator. In the first model (m1), passenger satisfaction is influenced by the price, facilities, and experience provided to passengers. This means that price, facilities, and experience can increase passenger satisfaction. In the second model (m2), satisfaction functions as a mediator that relates the influence of these variables to

loyalty. So, apart from the direct influence of factors such as price, facilities, experience on loyalty, indirect influence also occurs through passenger satisfaction. This study identifies that price, amenities, and experience have an effect on passenger loyalty by increasing satisfaction first. With a sample of 106 respondents, the results of this study emphasize that companies that want to increase passenger loyalty need to focus on factors that increase satisfaction.

E. Path Model

Fig 3: Path Model

F. Mediation Analysis Result

Table 6: Mediation Analysis Result

Type	Effect	Estimate	SE	β	z	P
Indirect	Price \Rightarrow Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.0421	0.0303	0.0393	1.39	0.164
	Facility \Rightarrow Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.0535	0.0447	0.0533	1.20	0.232
	Experience \Rightarrow Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.3330	0.0883	0.3171	3.77	<.001
Component	Price \Rightarrow Satisfaction	0.0921	0.0627	0.0913	1.47	0.142
	Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.4567	0.1060	0.4303	4.31	<.001
	Facility \Rightarrow Satisfaction	0.1171	0.0941	0.1239	1.24	0.213
	Experience \Rightarrow Satisfaction	0.7291	0.0935	0.7370	7.79	<.001
Direct	Price \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.1106	0.0691	0.1032	1.60	0.109
	Facility \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.1123	0.1034	0.1119	1.09	0.278
	Experience \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.3342	0.1280	0.3183	2.61	0.009
Total	Price \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.1527	0.0745	0.1425	2.05	0.040
	Facility \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.1658	0.1118	0.1653	1.48	0.138
	Experience \Rightarrow Loyalty	0.6672	0.1112	0.6354	6.00	<.001

Source: Data Processing

From table 6 it can be explained that:

➤ Direct effects

- **Price \Rightarrow Loyalty** (0.1106, p-value = 0.109) The direct effect of price on loyalty is **not significant** ($p > 0.05$). This shows that price alone is not enough to affect passenger loyalty. (**H1 is not proven**).
- **Facility \Rightarrow Loyalty** (0.1123, p = 0.278). The direct effect of facilities on loyalty was also **not significant** ($p > 0.05$). Facilities do not have a direct impact on loyalty. (**H2 is not proven**).
- **Experience \Rightarrow Loyalty** (0.3342, p = 0.009) The effect of direct experience on loyalty is significant ($p < 0.05$). Experience is a factor that directly affects loyalty. (**H3 proven**).

➤ Component Effect

- **Price \Rightarrow Satisfaction** (e = 0.0921, p = 0.142) The effect of price on satisfaction is **not significant** ($p > 0.05$). Prices do not contribute directly to passenger satisfaction levels. (**H4 is not proven**).
- **Facility \Rightarrow Satisfaction** (e = 0.1171, p = 0.213) The effect of facilities on satisfaction was **not significant** ($p > 0.05$). This means that facilities do not have a strong direct relationship with satisfaction levels. (**H5 is not proven**).
- **Experience \Rightarrow Satisfaction** (e = 0.7291, p < .001) The effect of experience on satisfaction is **significant** ($p < 0.05$). Experience makes a great contribution to increasing passenger satisfaction. (**H6 proven**).
- **Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty** (e = 0.4567, p < .001) Satisfaction has a **significant** effect on passenger loyalty ($p < 0.05$).

Satisfaction is an important variable that directly increases loyalty. (**H7 proven**).

➤ Indirect Effects

- **Price \Rightarrow Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty**. Estimated value: 0.0421, p-value: 0.164 (The effect of price on loyalty through satisfaction as mediation is not significant, because ($p > 0.05$)). This means that price does not have a significant indirect effect on loyalty through satisfaction, in this context, although price does affect satisfaction, the influence is not enough to increase passenger loyalty. So even if the price is cheaper or more expensive, it doesn't automatically make passengers more loyal, especially if satisfaction doesn't increase. (**H8 is not proven**).
- **Facility \Rightarrow Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty**. Estimate value: 0.0535, p-value: 0.232 (The effect of facilities on loyalty through satisfaction is also **not significant**, because ($p > 0.05$)). Facilities also have no indirect influence on loyalty through satisfaction, with this, even if the facilities are upgraded, such as more comfortable seats or up-to-date facilities, if this does not significantly increase passenger satisfaction, loyalty will not increase either. So facilities alone are not enough to build passenger loyalty without paying attention to their satisfaction. (**H9 is not proven**).
- **Experience \Rightarrow Satisfaction \Rightarrow Loyalty**. Estimate value: 0.3330, p-value: <0.001 (**significant**). Experience has a very strong indirect influence on loyalty through satisfaction. If a passenger's experience during the trip (e.g. friendly service, comfortable, punctual travel) increases satisfaction, then this will have a major impact on their loyalty. This shows that experience is a key factor, When passengers feel satisfied because of a good trip, they are more likely to be loyal passengers. (**H10 proven**).

➤ *Total Effect*

- **Price => Loyalty** (0.1527, p = 0.040) Overall, price has a **significant** influence on loyalty (p < 0.05), although the contribution is small.

- **Facility => Loyalty** (0.1658, p = 0.138) total facilities have **no significant** effect on loyalty (p > 0.05).
- **Experience => Loyalty** (0.6672, p < 0.001) Total experience has a **significant** influence on loyalty (p < 0.05).

➤ *Types of Mediation*

Table 7: Relationship Between Independent, Mediation and Dependent Variables

No	Variable Relationship	Indiret Effect (axb)	Direct Effect (c)	Direction	Information
1.	Price-Satisfaction-Loyalty	p=0,16>0.05, Insignifcant	p=0,109>0.05, Insignifcant	Unidirectional	No Effect mediation
2.	Facilities-Satisfaction-Loyalty	p=0,16>0.05, Insignifcant	p=0.278 >0.05, Insignifcant	Unidirectional	No Effect Mediation
3.	Experience-Satisfaction-Loyalty	p=0,001<0.05, Signifikan	p=0,009<0,05, Signifikan	Unidirectional	Complementary mediation

Source: Table 6

VI. DISCUSSION

Research [15] found that passenger experience has a significant effect on loyalty with a coefficient value of 0.6672. This study also shows that positive experiences contribute to satisfaction, with a probvalue of < 0.001, which shows that experience is a key factor in building loyalty, it can be concluded that this research is in line with research [15]

Research by Sofyan entitled "The Influence of Facilities and Service Quality on Loyalty" examines the variables of facilities and service quality that have a significant effect on passenger loyalty with a coefficient of 0.728 and service quality of 0.62, both of which have a positive effect on passenger loyalty. This result is in line with this study which shows that facilities contribute positively to passenger satisfaction and loyalty, with the loading factor value for facilities above 1.25. [9]

Another research by [6] entitled "The Influence of Service Quality, Price, and Passenger Value on Loyalty Through Satisfaction in BRT Trans Semarang Passengers" uses the iteration formula method, variables Service Quality (X1), Price (X2), Passenger Value (X3), Satisfaction (Y1), and Loyalty (Y2) [6] The results of the study also show that service quality, price, and passenger value have an impact on passenger loyalty, which is mediated by passenger satisfaction, this is evidenced by a greater indirect influence value than the direct influence on each variable, namely service quality (0.314>0.188), price (0.246>0.154), and passenger value (0.261>0.190). This is in line with this study because both found that passenger satisfaction plays an important role in increasing passenger loyalty.

VII. CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

A. *Conclusion*

- Of the 3 hypothesized variables that affect loyalty, directly only the experience variable has a significant effect, while the price and facilities have a significant effect.
- Of the 3 variables hypothesized to affect loyalty indirectly, only the experience variable had a significant effect, while the price and facility variables had no significant effect.
- The satisfaction variable has a significant effect on loyalty.
- The satisfaction variable does not mediate the effect of price and facilities on loyalty.
- The satisfaction variable only mediates the experience variable.
- The role of the satisfaction variable is only complementary.

B. *Policy Implications*

- A service must be created that is able to provide a memorable experience for passengers, because the practice is both directly and through the mediation of the satisfaction factor. Focus on the passenger experience: since experience has a direct influence on loyalty, try to make the passenger experience when using the service truly memorable and positive. For example, service that is friendly, fast, or makes passengers feel appreciated.
- Increase satisfaction: Since satisfaction mediates the influence of experience on loyalty, consistent efforts are needed to maintain and improve passenger satisfaction. For example, through improving service quality, quick response to passenger needs, as well as evaluation and improvement based on feedback from passengers.
- Don't focus too much on price or amenities. Price and amenities do not have a significant effect on loyalty. Therefore, focus more on more effective strategies, such as improving the good experience and things that can increase passenger satisfaction

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